

Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction in the Relationship between Employees Perception of Violation of Norms of Justice and Organizational Commitment

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Abstract

Purpose: The present research work was done to study the mediating role of job satisfaction in the relationship between employees' perception of violation of norms of justice and organizational commitment.

Design/Methodology/Approach: The study was done on 250 employees of Public and Private Organizations (125 from each). On the basis of an interview done on some of the employees from both the sectors i.e. Public and Private, a scale for measuring perceived violation of norms of justice was developed. For measuring other variables, standard scales were used. Data were collected through questionnaire method. For analysis, mediation analysis were done.

Findings: Results showed that job satisfaction mediated the relationship between employees' perception of violation of norms of justice and organizational commitment.

Practical Implications: The study has implications for scholars of organizational behavior, to look into the organizational problems from the perspective of employees i.e. what do the employees think of existing social norms.

Social Implications: This study shows that employees/humans are vital factors in the running/success of any organizations/society.

Originality: The research is original in the sense that it tries to compare employees' perception of Justice Norms in both Public and Private Organizations.

Keywords

Perception of Violation of Norms of Justice, Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment.

Introduction

An organization is a group of individuals who work together to achieve common goals and objectives, often with a structured approach and defined roles. An organization can be a private or public group such as a business, school, charity, government office etc. that has a clear goal and purpose. All organizations have a management structure that determines the relationship between different activities and the members and sub divides and assign roles.

Objective of study

To study the role of mediating variables i.e. job satisfaction on the relationship between 'perceived violation of norms' and outcome variables i.e. organizational commitment.

Review of Literature

Justice Concerns in Organizations

We can understand why justice is important by remembering that fairness concerns itself with what things get allocated and how these allocations take place. Thus, to say that justice matters are more or less synonymous with maintaining that people care about how they are with others. The roots of justice can be found in our inclination to affiliate with other people. This is also well explained by Sampson (1975) "Just solution-promote cohesion and order, including a state of psychological well-being while unjust solutions contribute to personal and social unrest and disorganization." Thus, Justice is essential for psychological functioning and welfare of the individual.

Issues relating to fairness become more salient in the case of organizational work setting. Theorists have recognized justice as a key organizational value (Lind and Tyler, 1988) - "the morale problem for years to come will be one of justice. The modern survey to maximally useful will centre more on problems of fairness procedures of payment of promotion and so forth, than on conditions of work as the closeness of supervisions per se." People become no less animated by justice when they arrive at work. In fact, concerns over injustice have provided impetus to the labour movement (Fantasia, 1988). Presently, the language of justice is shaping dialogue concerning global capitalism in developing nations (Greider, 1997).

Moreover, also research conducted across a variety of contexts (e. g., layoffs, drug testing, and pay cuts) in both laboratory and field settings demonstrates the importance of treating employees in a fair manner (Konovsky, 2000). Recent reviews and meta-analytic studies examining justice at the individual level indicate fairness is a correlate or predictor of a no. of important organizational outcomes. For example, perceptions of fairness have been positively associated with favorable employees attitudes and behaviours including organizational commitment, organizational support, OCBs, work performance, and trust in management (e. g., Cohen-Charash & Spector, 2001; Colquitt, Conlon, Wesson, Porter, & Ng, 2001;). However, when treated unfairly, employees are likely to react in unfavorable ways such as engaging in counterproductive work behaviours (e. g., damaging company property or spreading rumors), turnover, and theft (Cropanzano, Byrne, Bobocel, & Rupp, 2001).

Thus, it is clear that justice matters and that people care about justice for a variety of reasons (i.e., people may even defend the view that justice is omnipresent and that the pursuit of justice is in itself a guiding and moral directive in our social lives.

Different Norms of Justice

At most general level, organizational justice is an area of psychological inquiry that focuses on perceptions of fairness in the workplace. Instances of justice take a variety of forms and researchers have throughout the last few decades devoted much attention to distinguishing among different "types" of justice (e.g., Bies & Moag, 1986; Greenberg &

Colquitt, 2005; Thiabou & Walker, 1975). More precisely, justice involves issues of distribution, treatment, formal and informal decision-making procedures, and so forth. So it can be said that individuals' perceptions of fairness in organizational settings have been conceptualized regarding at least three separate types of organizational justice. The first category centered on:

Distributive Justice: It is a kind of justice in which fairness was defined regarding the outcomes of a resource allocation decision. Three rules have been identified as the basis people use for distributive justice i.e. equity, equality and need.

Procedural Justice: In the organizational context, procedural justice is considered a valuable resource in social exchange. Procedural justice is an appraisal of the process by which an allocation decision is (or was) made. Evidence now shows that when people believe that decision-making processes are unjust, they show less commitment to their employers, more theft, higher turnover intentions, lower performance, and fewer cooperative citizenship behaviors (for recent reviews, see Cropanzano & Greenberg, 1997).

Interactional Justice: The literature on employee-employer relations shows that an employee expects the organization to treat him/her with respect, dignity, honesty and to extend equal treatment to all members (Janssens, Sels, & Van den Brande, 2003; Kickul & Liao Troth, 2003). Bies & Moag (1986) referred to this notion as interactional justice, which is the perception of the quality of treatment an employee receives when policies and procedures are implemented in the workplace. Perceptions of interactional justice play a role in the determination of employees' attitudes and behaviour (Cohen-Charash & Spector, 2001; Colquitt, Conlon, Wesson, Porter, & Yee Ng, 2001).

As the literature reviews show that a no. of researches have done relating different types of justice to the different type of outcomes, but meager studies is indicating the relationship of overall justice to organizational outcomes.

Responses to Violation of Norms of Justice:

Overall, the result of studies done, suggests that organizational justice may be predictive of different attitudes and behaviours (Greenberg, 1990). The different reactions are like outcome satisfaction, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, trust, agent-referenced evaluations, withdrawal organizational citizenship behaviour, adverse reactions and much more like that.

The present research undertakes to study how organizational level outcome variables such as and job satisfaction get influenced when there is the perception of violation of norms in the organizations. The reason for taking these variables lies in their importance to organizations as a whole because if the employees in the organization do not feel perceived organizational support. then, it will adversely affect the both growth and production of the organizations. Moreover, the issues become more salient in the context of Public and Private Organizations.

Organizational Commitment: Porter Steers, Mowday and Bolian (1974) defined organizational commitment as the relative strength of an individual's identification and involvements with a particular organization. They have characterized it by three factors. These factors are, strong belief in the goals and values of the organization and acceptance of those organization's goals and values, a willingness to exert considerable effort on behalf of the organization, and a strong desire to maintain membership in the organization.

A review of organizational commitment research literature by Meyer and Allen (1991), and corroborated by Dunham, Gruba and Castaneda (1994), identified three types of organizational commitment: affective, continuance and normative.

Affective commitment is defined as employee emotional attachment to, identification with, and involvement in the organization and its goals.

Continuance commitment is defined as willingness to remain in an organization because of personal investment in the form of non-transferable investments such as close working relationships with co-workers, retirement investments and career investments, acquired job skills which are unique to a particular organization, years of employment in a particular organization, involvement in the community in which the employer is located, and other benefits that make it too costly for one to leave and seek employment elsewhere.

Normative commitment is induced by a feeling of obligation to remain with an organization. Such a feeling of obligation often results from what Wiener (1982) characterized as "generalized value of loyalty and duty."

Common to all of the three types of commitment is the view that commitment is a psychological state that (a) characterizes the employee's relationship with the organization, and (b) has implication for the decision to continue or discontinue membership in the organization.

Organizational commitment is associated with many important work attitudes and behaviours, such as job satisfaction and work performance (Meyer, Paunonen, Gellatly, Goffin & Jackson, 1989; Mowday et.al., 1982).

Job Satisfaction: Locke (1976) gives a comprehensive definition of job satisfaction as a "pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experience". McCue (1999) suggested that job satisfaction is an important theoretical and practical concept because it may affect the ability of employees to deal with job demands successfully and perform effectively. At the organizational level, low job satisfaction has been linked to increased absenteeism, job turnover, decreased task performance and declining employee morale (Mathieu & Hamel, 1989; McGee & Cavender, 1984).

There are three important dimensions to job satisfaction. First, job satisfaction is an emotional response to a job response to a job situation. Second, job satisfaction is often determined by how well outcome meet or exceed expectations. Third, job satisfaction represents several related attitudes like the work itself, pay, promotional of opportunity, supervision and co workers.

Thus it can be stated that Job Satisfaction, for the most part is positioned either as a determinant of workplace behavior (e.g. independent variable) or as a desirable outcome in its own right (dependent variable). So, there is the need to look the relationships of various situational and dispositional characteristics and organizational outcomes e.g. the role of job satisfaction as a mediating variable between perceived violation of norms of justice and outcome variables like OCB, organizational commitment and intention to leave.

Methodology

Sample: The present study will be based on a sample of 250 employees. The sample will include employees from both sectors i.e. public and private. Data will be collected through questionnaire method.

Development of scale for measuring Perception of Justice: To develop a scale for measuring perception of justice in the organization by the employees, pilot interviews were conducted on the employees. The total numbers of employees were 20, out of which 12 were of private, and eight were from the public. By answers given to some issues, items were formed. Finally, following no. of the articles was taken from administration:

Distributive Justice: 26

Procedural Justice: 19

Interactional Justice: 18

Organizational Commitment: was measured with the scale developed by Cook & Wall (1980) The scale has 9 items.

Job Satisfactions: It was measured by using the five items taken from an 18-items index of global satisfaction developed by Brayfield & Rahe (1951) and tested by Agho, Mueller, and Price.

An example of the item:

Most of the time, I am very excited about my job.

Result and Discussion

Table:1 Mediation analysis for Job Satisfaction: Predicting Organizational Commitment with Perception of Violation of Norms of Justice (N=250).

Predictors	F	Beta(β)	t
Perception of Violation of Norms of Justice	Mediator Variable: Job Satisfaction		
	121.27	-0.67	-10.06**
Perception of Violation of Norms of Justice	Dependent Variable: Organizational Commitment		
	20.39	-0.37	-4.81**
PVN, Job Satisfaction	Dependent Variable: Organizational Commitment		
	11.47	PVN= -0.34 JS=-0.21	-4.39** -2.48**

Note *p<0.05; **p<0.01; PVN= Perception of Violation of Norms of Justice.
JS=Job Satisfaction

Conclusion

Justice is important to our social as well as organizational functioning as is explained by the fact that the concept of justice (as well as its violation) often dictates our daily experiences and discussions (e.g., Finkel, 2001; Folger, 1984). This research has been done with the purpose of understanding how does the job satisfaction mediate the relationship between perception of violation of norms of justice in the organizations by the employees and personal level outcome variables organizational commitment.

In general, the results supported most of the developed hypothesized relationship. Since in our study, the focus was to study employees' perception of violation of norms of justice, so the two organizations were taken. Of the two agencies, one was from public sector while other was from the private sector. Results supported that private organization employees will perceive less violation of norms of justice in comparison to the public organization employees. Studies conducted in an organizational context, taking Public/Private sector as antecedent factors have found that these organizations differ regarding climate and norms. (Roy, 1974; de, 1974; Prasad, 1979; Sinha, 1973); organizational activities and reinforcement patterns control of economy, autonomy, layers of management, communication network, etc. These differences generated a complicated system of feelings, expectations, perceptions, attitudes and values in their employees which in turn influences outcome variables organizational commitment.

Result (Table No.1) showed that job satisfaction mediated the relationship between perceived violation of norms of justice and outcome variable organizational commitment. Thus, result supported the hypotheses. The explanation could be that if the employees in the organization perceive that they are not getting fair amount of treatment in terms of distribution of resources, implementation of rules and respect from the co-workers and organization then they develop a negative emotional state which is the sign of dissatisfaction with the job. And this job dissatisfaction influenced the employees identification with the organizational goals and values, thus, reducing the organizational commitment (Feinstein and Vondrasek, 2006). This finding is in line with the work of earlier scholar who found that perceived organizational justice influenced the employees' organizational commitment by mediating through their level of perceived organization support (Wayne and colleagues, 1997; Rhoades et. al 2001; Loi et.al.2006).

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